

Dynamic Analysis of a Novel Wormly-Structured Snake Robot

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Abstract: Nowadays snake robots play incredible roles in robotics. Despite the wide range of use, they suffer from some main disadvantages; Not only they are not flexible enough, but also large diameter and utilizing unsuitable joints increase the probability of getting stuck in curvy paths. Additionally, they are usually designed for special tasks not for general issues, for example they will face dynamic limitations in working freely.

In this work the prepared robot has overcome the above disadvantages, through the use of high density covered pipes as its frame. Our robot claims high flexibility due to the use of a sophisticated joint for movement in tight curvy routs. Furthermore, there is no need to any extra space for movement despite the robots introduced in prior works. It is designed to be used in various sites such as pipelines and gearboxes as a problem recognizer under predefined circumstances. Here, the special movement in three phases is proposed for making the robot act like a worm. Within this work the dynamic movements of the robot is first modelled in state-space, then the movement is analyzed in three recognized phases mentioned above added by illustrative block diagrams and figures.

Keywords: Snake robot, dynamic, wormy movement, state-space

1. Introduction

Snake robots can be used in Industry [1], security and defence [2], medical research [3- 4].

There were previous works on this phenomenon. For instance, various types of models have been developed by Miler [5]. In [6] the movement force is applied via wheels on snake robot with specific characteristics and for different challenging environmental situation.

Serpentine robots were become more well-liked for overcoming the earlier robots disadvantages [7]. CPG (Distributed Central Pattern) control was proposed in prior mobile robots for making optimized algorithms [8]. In 2003, a snake robot was proposed to be utilized in small pipelines whose movement algorithm suffered from being wavy [9]. Being dependent on pipeline body properties, makes it so limited and feeble in wide range applications. Furthermore, having a wire connection between the robot and outside for power supply and

controlling the process, there was high threat of being locked in the pipes.

Another robot was invented with high flexibility, which had got many controlling motors to be capable enough in most of cases particularly in pipelines. Nevertheless it was suffering from being controlled with wire, moreover, it needed to have considerable extra space for crawling inside pipelines [10].

Robotic systems MRINSPECT series were presented in pipelines by analyzing dynamics in realistic conditions in 2007, even though; it needed to be adaptable to characteristic of pipelines [11].

Fig.1: The Wireless Wormly-Structured Snake robot.

An essential requirement of the considered robot is flexibility. Utilizing the special joints, the proposed robot is 270 degree flexible with, allowing us to use it in curvy spaces as it is shown in Fig.1. Because of small diameter it is capable of being used in tight paths, so as a problem recognizer, it can crawl inside the pipelines, gearboxes and even inside the human body, if decreased in size. Regarding all these, this robot can be used in the fields of industry and medical research.

Fig.2: Schematic of the proposed snake robot movement.

As it was mentioned the proposed robot has the capability of being controlled in the pipelines. By using soft nylon coverage, it has full waterproof system and mobility in slippery locations. It can resist a pressure of up to 12 atmospheres because of high density of poly ethylene pipes as its frame.

Due to the robot's utilization in distant pipelines, it should be able to distinguish the current location. Accordingly, it is equipped with Signal Tracer for tracking down in emergency situations. In order to use it in the far distance without any connection with outside world, the system is equipped with wireless control.

It contains four infrared LEDs surrounding the camera resulting in high resolution photos and video from area in the darkness. These diodes will aid us to recognize the problem better.

The safety is another subjective issue. While having no access to the robot, we must be sure it is not got stuck or stopped in the midway. In order to fulfil such a goal miniature gears involved with motor shaft are added to the system to reduce the unpredicted saturation in dc motor, which in worse condition may lead to an inevitable phenomena such as dc motor or IC breakdown.

As it was mentioned this robot might be used as a fiberscope to recognize any probable problems inside the gearboxes with upcoming obstacles.

Against the possible chemical harm on blocks or even interior drivers, a chemical proof coverage is added on the robot. Therefore, in hazardous areas it could perform tasks efficiently.

The dynamic analysis of the robot is represented in three distinguished phases as explained below.

2. Phase Distribution

Having neglected fractional effects and some environmental factors, the schematics of the robot's movement in 3 distinguished phases is depicted in Fig.2 in which the robot has moved D unit in forward direction at the end of considered movement algorithm. In this figure the arrow oriented to right shows a CCW(counter clockwise) turning of crew to force the robot in forward path, the opposite are pointing to the left indicate a CW(clockwise) turning applying a reverse force for carrying the rest of the robot's body. According to calculated dynamics of robot, state-space dynamics of each phase with refined block diagram is given underneath.

2.1 Phase 1

Torque produced from Driver 1, makes Driver 1 work in Forward mode whose produced torque (not being saturated) is equal to:

$$K_1 i_{a_1} = J_1 \frac{d^2 \theta_1}{dt^2} + f_1 \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} \quad (1)$$

J_1 , f_1 and K_1 represent the moment of inertia of the rotor, damping (friction) of the mechanical system and (back)-electromotive force constants. However, the outer force factor like friction has been neglected for simplicity of calculation. By doing KVL for considered DC motor Equation (2) will appear [12].

$$u(t) = R_{a_1} i_{a_1} + L_{a_1} \frac{d i_{a_1}}{dt} + v_{b_1}(t) \quad (2)$$

R_{a_1} , L_{a_1} and $v_{b_1}(t)$ indicate the armature resistance, armature reluctance and the back electromotive force $v_{b_1}(t)$ contains the below proportion to angular replacement through Equation (3):

$$v_{b_1}(t) = K_{b_1} \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} \quad (3)$$

By putting Equation (4) and Equation (3) in previous ones from Equation (1-2).The final result will be presented as Equation (5) and Equations (6).

$$\theta_1 = 2\pi D_1 \quad (4)$$

$$u(t) = R_{a_1} i_{a_1} + L_{a_1} \frac{d i_{a_1}}{dt} + 2\pi K_{b_1} \frac{dD_1}{dt} \quad (5)$$

$$K_1 i_a = 2\pi J_1 \frac{dD_1}{dt} + 2\pi f_1 \frac{dD_1}{dt} \quad (6)$$

Defining X as illustrated in Equation (7), results in Equations (8) to (10). Because the main purpose is finding the state-space of Phase1, the final equations for reaching the state-space are available:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} i_{a_1} & D_1 & \dot{D}_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$u(t) = R_{a_1} x_1 + L_{a_1} \dot{x}_1 + 2\pi K_{b_1} x_3 \quad (8)$$

$$K_1 x_1 = 2\pi J_1 \dot{x}_3 + 2\pi f_1 x_3 \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{x} = \begin{bmatrix} -R_{a_1}/L_{a_1} & 0 & -2\pi K_{b_1}/L_{a_1} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ K_1/2\pi J_1 & 0 & -f_1/J_1 \end{bmatrix} x(t)$$

$$+ \begin{bmatrix} 1/L_{a_1} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u(t)$$

$$y(t) = [0 \ 1 \ 0]x(t) \quad (10)$$

The block diagram of the calculated state-space is illustrated in Fig. 3 in which Disp. Output 1 stands for Displacement as output in first Driver. In this phase a voltage of 7.4v is set as input by means of interior batteries. Additionally, there is a driver IC between Power source and Dc motor. Accordingly, equivalent structure has been located in considered block diagram. The gain factors applied to diagram are given in TABLE I.

Fig.3: Block diagram of Phase 1, Driver 1 represents the output.

Fig.4: The displacement vs. time dimension in Driver 1 under forward turn.

TABLE I: Labelled numerical coefficients for formulas [12].

J	0.01 kg.m ²
K_b, K	0.1 N.ms
f	0.01 Nm/A
R	1 ohm
L	0.5 H

The graph of displacement vs. time for Phase 1 (forward turning) is indicated in Fig. 4 showing a continuous increase in 'D' while turning forward, but this increase will be stopped after a short while. As shown in Fig.5 Robot contains threaded bar with limited length. Due to this equipment the process of Drive 1 movement via Driver 1 will take apart in specific time duration until the end of illustrated threaded bar.

Fig.5: Threaded bar as output force in carrying drives.

2.2 Phase 2

In this phase, two drivers work simultaneously in the opposite direction of each other to carry the middle drive (drive 2) to forward direction as mentioned in Fig.2. Second phase will occur for both dc motors. In this phase the interaction of the two drivers to each other is neglected in order to simplify equations. The torque relations for both systems have been calculated by applying the same methods:

$$K_2 i_a = J_2 \frac{d^2 \theta_2}{dt^2} + f_2 \frac{d\theta_2}{dt} \quad (11)$$

$$-K_1 i_a = J_1 \frac{d^2 \theta_1}{dt^2} + f_1 \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} \quad (12)$$

The minus sign in Equation (12) indicates the reverse movement of motor in which the counter clockwise direction is considered as positive in systems equation and opposite situation for clockwise direction. the KVL is significantly different from Phase1 since two estimated circuits of dc motors are imagined in series with a voltage of 14.4 on polarity of circuit so the result is as follows[1].

$$u(t) = (R_{a_1} + R_{a_2}) i_a + (L_{a_1} + L_{a_2}) \frac{d i_a}{dt} + v_{b_1}(t) + v_{b_2}(t) \quad (13)$$

Where:

$$v_{b_2}(t) = K_{b_2} \frac{d\theta_2}{dt},$$

$$v_{b_1}(t) = K_{b_1} \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} \quad (14)$$

$$\theta_1 = 2\pi D_1, \theta_2 = 2\pi D_2 \quad (15)$$

Substituting the value, in Equation (16) and Equation (17) we have:

$$-K_1 i_a = 2\pi J_1 \frac{d^2 D_1}{dt^2} + 2\pi f_1 \frac{dD_1}{dt} \quad (16)$$

$$K_2 i_a = 2\pi J_2 \frac{d^2 D_2}{dt^2} + 2\pi f_2 \frac{dD_2}{dt} \quad (17)$$

Defining X as Equation (18), results in Equation (19) to Equation (22).

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} i_a & D_1 & \dot{D}_1 & D_2 & \dot{D}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$-K_1 x_1 = 2\pi J_1 \dot{x}_2 + 2\pi f_1 x_2 \quad (19)$$

$$K_2 x_1 = 2\pi J_2 \dot{x}_5 + 2\pi f_2 x_5 \quad (20)$$

$$u(t) = (R_{a_1} + R_{a_2}) x_1 + (L_{a_1} + L_{a_2}) \dot{x}_1 + v_{b_1}(t) + v_{b_2}(t) \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -(R_{a_1} + R_{a_2}) / (L_{a_1} + L_{a_2}) & 0 & -2\pi K_{b_1} / (L_{a_1} + L_{a_2}) & 0 & -2\pi K_{b_2} / (L_{a_1} + L_{a_2}) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -K_{b_1} / 2\pi J_1 & 0 & -f_1 / J_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ K_{b_2} / 2\pi J_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -f_2 / J_2 \end{bmatrix} x(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 / (L_{a_1} + L_{a_2}) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u(t) \quad (22)$$

$$y(t) = [0 \quad 0 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad 1] x(t)$$

Based on the state-space in Equation (22), block diagram is shown in Fig.6 and the displacement vs. time for Phase 2 is illustrated in Fig.7 in which the first graph shows the movement of first driver in CW (clockwise) as carrier. Next graph in same figure demonstrates the second driver in CCW (counter clockwise) mode.

2.3 Phase 3

Last part (Phase 3) is just like the initial task. The only difference is in its torque sign. Due to Newton's second rule we have:

Fig.8: (a) The drawn block diagram responded to Driver 2, by some changes in its functions (b) The replacement proportional to time domain.

4. References

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